

Assessment of Seismic and Wind Load Resistance in High-Rise Building Designs: A Comparison of Geometric Shapes

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Abstract

As the world moves towards modernisation, population growth has led to one of the most pressing challenges - limited land availability. To address this issue, the conventional approach of horizontal building designs needs to be reconsidered and the focus should shift to high-rise buildings. This study explores the design of a 50-storey high-rise building using different geometric shapes, namely rectangular, square, triangular, circular and elliptical. The design is based on keeping parameters such as floor area, column size, beam size and slab thickness constant across all shapes. Following the design process, various loads - seismic, wind, live and dead - are applied to the structure to simulate real world conditions. The primary objective of this work is to evaluate and determine the most stable and feasible building form for high-rise structures in the most critical seismic (Zone V) and wind (Zone V) zones. The shear force (F_y) on the beam of different building shapes is minimum for the elliptical shape building i.e. 4.838kN. The shear force (F_y) on the column of different building shapes is maximum for the rectangular shape building i.e. 88.301kN and minimum for the elliptical shape building i.e. 25.498kN. The bending moment (kNm) on the beam of different shapes of building is maximum for the elliptical shape building, and minimum for the rectangular shape building. i.e.13,939kNm. The bending moment (kNm) on the column of different shapes of building is maximum for the rectangular shape building. i.e.149.656kNm, and minimum for the elliptical shape building. i.e.37.083 kNm. The displacement (mm) on the beam of different shapes of building minimum for the elliptical shape building. i.e. 231.377 mm. The displacement (mm) on the column of different shapes of building is minimum for the elliptical shape building. i.e. 226.707 mm. The stress (N/mm²) on different shapes of building is and minimum for the elliptical shape building. i.e. 0.0034N/mm².The safest shape of 50 storey high rise building in seismic zone v and in wind zone v is elliptical shape. The study shows that the safest shape of a 50-storey high-rise building in seismic zone v and in wind zone v is the elliptical shape. In addition, the study focuses on assessing the stress distribution and structural performance of each shape under these extreme loading conditions. The results are expected to provide valuable insights into the optimal design of high-rise buildings for seismic and wind resistance, contributing to safer and more efficient urban development.

Keywords: *High rise building, Seismic load, Wind load, ZoneV, critical, shapes.*

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Introduction

In 21st century due to huge population the no of areas in units are decreasing day by day. Few years back the population was not so huge so they used to stay in horizontal system (due to large area available per person). But now a day's people prefer vertical system (high rise building due to shortage of area). In high rise building we should consider all the forces acting on a building, its own weight as well as the soil bearing capacity. For external forces acting on the building the beam, column and reinforcement should be good enough to counteract these forces successfully. And the ground should be good enough to transfer the load successfully to the foundation. If we do so much calculation for a tall building manually, it will take more time and human error can occur. So using STAAD-PRO will make it easy. STAAD-PRO can solve typical problems such as static analysis, seismic analysis and natural frequency. These types of problems can be solved with STAAD-PRO along with IS-CODE. Tall buildings, usually designed for office or commercial use, are among the most significant spatial definitions in the architectural history of twentieth-century American urbanism.

Aim of the Study

The authors formulated the following research objectives:

- To contribute to the development of design guidelines for high-rise buildings, focusing on the effect of different building shapes in controlling wind and seismic loads, and to provide a reference for architects, engineers, developers and students.
- To design and analyse a 50-storey high-rise building in accordance with the relevant Indian Standards (IS Codes) for structural integrity and

safety.

- To analyse the earthquake resistance of the building as per IS 1893-2016 (Part I) Criteria for Earthquake Resistant Structures.

Literature Review

Bhatta Charjee and Nagender, (2007): Computer Aided Analysis and Design of Multi-Storey Buildings. STAAD Pro has the ability to calculate the required reinforcement for any concrete section, demonstrating its power in structural design. This highlights the importance of using STAAD Pro software in building design.

Merrick and Bitsuamlak, (2009): Shape Effects on the Wind-Induced Response of High-Rise Buildings. Elliptical, triangular and rectangular buildings were found to be more susceptible to high torsional loads. This study provides valuable insights into the choice of shape for high-rise buildings.

Parasonis and Keizikas, (2011): The relationship between the shape of a building and its energy performance. This research shows that the geometric efficiency of a building is influenced by both its size and proportions, and provides guidance on the ideal building shape and size ratio.

Sinha et al. (2014): Loading Conditions in High-Rise Buildings. High rise buildings are subject to several loading conditions, with wind and seismic forces being the most critical for tall structures. Wind Loads: Wind load analysis is particularly important for buildings over 30 storeys. The International Building Code (IBC) requires the wind load to be calculated taking into account the wind speed, exposure and height of the building. The shape of the building influences the distribution of wind pressure across the façade. Buildings with more irregular

shapes can experience higher vortex shedding and wind-induced vibrations.

Mohammad Naser, (2015): Seismic analysis and design of a hospital building using equivalent static analysis. Initially, the building was designed without considering seismic loads according to IS456:2000. Subsequently, the building was re-designed to consider earthquake loads as per IS1893:2002, providing insight into seismic analysis and design considerations.

Anupam and Rajmani, (2015): Analysis of wind and seismic loads for different shapes of high-rise buildings. For a 15-storey building, the circular and triangular shapes were found to be the most stable under wind and seismic loads, providing important insights for shape selection.

Sayali and Gawali, (2015): Effects of Shape on the Wind-Induced Response of High-Rise Buildings. The gust factor method used to estimate the wind-induced response highlights the importance of accurately considering wind loads on flexible structures, which helps in designing wind-resistant buildings.

Ghosh et al. (2015): Rectangular and square shapes: These are the most commonly used shapes in high-rise buildings due to their ease of construction and efficient use of space. However, they often experience significant torsional movements under wind or seismic loads, requiring careful design of shear walls or core structures.

Zhang et al., (2016); Circular or cylindrical shapes: Circular buildings tend to perform well under wind loads due to their aerodynamic shape, which reduces wind-induced torsion and drag. These shapes also improve the efficiency of the structural design in terms of material use and wind resistance.

Bhalchandra and P. Alone, (2017): Study on seismic analysis of high-rise buildings using software: This study points out that due to unsymmetrical building geometry, modes are less effective in resisting seismic forces in the X-direction, especially for 50-storey buildings.

Rathore et al. (2017): These buildings may be more architecturally appealing, but they often lead to vortex shedding and unbalanced wind

forces, requiring sophisticated computational analysis for load distribution. The geometric shape of a building plays a major role in determining its response to dynamic forces, such as wind and seismic activity. Research has investigated how different shapes affect factors such as load distribution, torsional behaviour and overall stability.

Nicola et al. (2017) investigated the behaviour of slender other shapes, providing insight into the influence of shape on structural behaviour. Impact of wind load with shape of high-rise buildings : Circular buildings are found to be more effective and less affected by wind loads due to their smooth surface, which reduces friction and wind resistance.

Thilakarathna et al. (2018): This study assesses the seismic performance of a high-rise building designed primarily to resist different levels of lateral wind loads. A 40-storey dual system building was selected for the case study, where the lateral load is resisted by a combination of a reinforced concrete core wall and a special moment resisting frame. The building is assumed to be located in a moderate seismic zone and is designed for wind loads based on three wind speed levels (low, moderate and high) representing different global wind zones. The study evaluates the seismic performance of these three design cases using Nonlinear Response History Analysis (NLRHA) to assess inelastic seismic requirements. The results show that the level of wind design load influences the seismic performance of high-rise buildings with dual systems. Therefore, even when wind loads dominate the design, a thorough performance-based seismic assessment is essential to ensure overall structural safety and integrity.

Reddy & Kumar, (2019): Seismic Analysis of High-Rise Buildings (G+30) Using ETABS Lateral displacements were found to be higher in zone 5 compared to zones 4, 3 and 2, contributing to the understanding of the seismic behaviour of high-rise buildings.

Nasser Al-Azri et al., (2020): Reducing Thmance-Based Wind Design (PBWD), which considers inelastic behaviour under extreme wind loads in high-rise buildings. Unlike Performance-Based Seismic Design (PBSD),

inelastic wind design lacks sufficient research and guidelines. PBWD typically relies on wind tunnel tests to generate time-history wind loads. However, conducting these tests for early stage structural designs may not be feasible due to design modifications and associated costs. To address these challenges, the study focused on: the use of a *RW* factor in initial designs to account for inelastic behaviour; the generation of time-history wind loads from power spectral density (PSD) functions for inelastic analysis, including vertical distribution and maximum directional load occurrence; and a case study to evaluate wind resistance performance for a reinforced concrete building using *RW* factors of 1, 2 and 3.

A recent study (Patel et al., 20-24) proposes an advanced load distribution model that incorporates geometry and material behaviour to ensure efficient structural design. Dead and live

loads: Although dead and live loads are less critical than shear forces, they still require detailed analysis, especially in irregularly shaped buildings where load distribution may be uneven.

Methodology

The following materials are used during the research work - Geometry, Section Property, Material Constant, Member Specification, Support, Load, Analysis Instruction, Post Processing Command, Design Command.

Flow Chart

Define the geometry of a structure, assign material properties, specify supports and loads, select the appropriate analysis method (such as linear static, dynamic or buckling), perform the analysis and then interpret the results to design structural elements such as beams and columns, all within the software interface.

Figure 1. Flow Chart of the Present Study

Results and Discussion

Figure 2. Shape of Building V/S Shear Force in Beam

Figure 3. Shape of Building V/S Shear Force in Column

Figure 4. Shape of Building V/S Bending Moment in Beam

Figure 5. Shape of Building V/S Bending Moment in Column

Figure 6. Shape of Building V/S Displacement in Beam

Figure 7. Shape of Building V/S Displacement in Column

Figure 8. Shape of Building V/S Stress in Building

Conclusions

The shear force (F_y) on the column of different shapes of building is maximum for the rectangular shape building, i.e. 88,301 kN, and minimum for the elliptical shape building, i.e. 25,498kN.

The bending moment (kNm) on the column of different shapes of building is maximum for the rectangular shape building i.e. 149.656kNm, and minimum for the elliptical shape building i.e. 37.083 kNm.

The safest shape of a 50 storey high-rise building in seismic zone v and wind zone v is the elliptical shape.

These results indicate the relative performance of different building shapes under seismic and wind load conditions, with the elliptical shape being the most stable.

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